

A Study on the Existence of Scandium Alum with Sc^{46}

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Distribution study with Sc^{46} as tracer and ammonium ferric alum as host lattice at 4° shows that the uptake obeys homogeneous distribution law over a wide range of concentration, indicating the uptake through mixed crystal formation. In the analogy of scandium with iron, the uptake through mixed crystal formation supports the existence of the unknown scandium alum. The finding has been supported by the study of a known system by selecting a guest like In^{114} , where partition factor is as low as in scandium and where ammonium indium alum is well known. From -2° onwards, the value of distribution factor, D , though constant at a particular temperature, assumes increasing values. The value is maximum at 4° . On further increasing the temperature, the value of D assumes a diminishing trend. At 20° the constancy of D vanishes. It has been argued that scandium alum is stable below 4° .

Mendeleef predicted the properties of ekaboron long before the discovery of scandium in 1879. One of his outstanding predictions was that scandium would not form any alum. Since then nothing has been reported about the existence of scandium alum. Non-formation of scandium alum is attributed to its somewhat larger ionic radius. Incidentally, the value of ionic radius for indium is nearly the same and ammonium indium alum is well known. There is no reason why scandium should not also form alum with ammonium as a monovalent cation. Failure in isolating the alum may be ascribed to the following reasons: (i) its high solubility, (ii) the stable phase at the working temperature comprising anhydrous double salt $\text{M}_2^{+1} \text{SO}_4$, $\text{Sc}_2(\text{SO}_4)$ or (iii) the very unstable nature of the scandium alum. It can only manifest its existence when carried through morphologically analogous host lattice. The present investigation deals with a study of the nature of uptake of Sc^{46} as tracer with some selected host alum as carrier; it may provide some clues regarding the existence of the alum and help us to gather informations so as to make an attempt towards isolation of such an interesting compound. Ammonium ferric alum was selected as the carrier because of its high solubility.

EXPERIMENTAL

Scandium⁴⁶ (85 days) and indium¹¹⁴ (50 days) were supplied by Messrs. N. V. Phillips Dupher. Natural scandium and indium used in this investigation were of spec. pure quality. In case where these were used in tracer concentration, the molarity was calculated from the specific activity of the radioactive sample from supplier's report. In our study with somewhat larger amount of inactive scandium, a stock solution, prepared in the following way, was used. Scandium oxide, supplied by Messrs. Johnson and Mathey Company, was ignited, weighed, and dissolved in HCl. Scandium⁴⁶ was then added. To effect a thorough mixing of scandium⁴⁶ tracer with inactive scandium, scandium hydroxide was precipitated by passing gaseous ammonia. It was freed of Cl^- ion by

washing with ammoniacal water. The scandium hydroxide was then dissolved in H_2SO_4 and the acidity was made to one normal. Where finite quantities of indium were used, metallic indium of spec. pure quality, as supplied by Messrs. Johnson and Mathey company, was dissolved in H_2SO_4 and a stock solution was conveniently prepared. Ammonium ferric alum used was of E. Merek G. R. quality.

Procedure.—A saturated solution of ammonium ferric alum in 1*N*- H_2SO_4 containing ammonium dichromate and the tracer ion was made at the required temperature. Same portions of this solution were added to different quantities of weighed ammonium ferric alum taken in L-shaped tubes provided with sockets and cones fitted at the mouth. The horizontal portions of the tubes were immersed in the thermostat and the vertical portions clamped to the shaking unit. This arrangement was found very convenient for the following reasons: (a) It did not allow any moisture to enter the system. (b) It guarded against any spilling of radioactive solution in the bath. (c) It helped separate the solid from solution by fitting a suitable adapter for filtration through sintered glass under pump in an atmosphere free of moisture. The solid alum was dissolved by gentle warming and then cooled to the room temperature. Supersaturation was broken by shaking for sometime; the contents of the tubes were shaken for 3 days, a period found sufficient for attainment of equilibrium by the system. The solid was separated from the solution by filtration through sintered glass under pump, dissolved in H_2SO_4 , and its activity determined in a liquid counter. Iron was estimated in the usual way in the mother liquor.

Activity was measured from the solid phase due to its low uptake in this case. Moreover, ammonium ferric alum is highly soluble and when it crystallises from solution, a considerable decrease in volume takes place. That is why neither the mother liquor could be washed out of the crystals in the usual way, nor the volume of the mother liquor could be known so as to measure the activity and the iron present in it. So a correction for the mother liquor adhering to the solid was introduced to compute the uptake of the tracer ion by the host lattice. Ammonium dichromate was added before crystallisation of the alum. The amount of dichromate present in the solid after separation from the solution is a measure of the mother liquor adhering to the solid phase. Dichromate in the solid was measured in the usual way. It was found by sets of trial experiments under identical condition of crystallisation that ammonium dichromate was not adsorbed by ammonium ferric alum.

Values of D' were calculated from the following expression:

$$D = \left(\frac{\text{tracer}}{\text{carrier}} \right)_{\text{solid}} / \left(\frac{\text{tracer}}{\text{carrier}} \right)_{\text{solution}}$$

Results of our investigation are recorded in the tables and in Figs. 1 and 2.

DISCUSSION

D values in Table I show that uptake of scandium increases with increase in concentration of scandium. When the concentration of scandium in the initial solution is below $10^{-2}M$, no appreciable uptake occurs. With increase in the concentration of tracer ion we find that D values, though constant at a particular concentration, go on increasing.

1. Henderson and Kracek, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 738.

TABLE I

Co-precipitation of scandium with ammonium ferric alum at $4^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Conc. of Sc.	Alum pptd.	Solid phase.		Sc. uptake.**	D_4
		* Gross activity.	Adhered mother liq.†		
$3.3 \times 10^{-2} M$	47.60%	8.24%	6.12%	2.12%	0.028
	57.10	10.10	8.16	1.94	0.015
	62.60	14.70	10.20	5.50	0.029
	66.80	21.50	16.30	5.20	0.027
					Av. 0.023
1.2×10^{-4}	47.40	9.10	4.40	4.47	0.058
	56.20	15.50	10.30	5.20	0.043
	63.30	20.30	13.20	7.10	0.044
	71.40	22.00	14.70	7.30	0.031
					Av. 0.042
2.6×10^{-2}	44.30	12.42	5.50	6.92	0.094
	59.04	18.23	8.20	10.09	0.078
	66.50	28.38	13.70	14.70	0.087
					Av. 0.086
3.5×10^{-2}	33.80	8.14	3.70	4.44	0.091
	43.00	13.30	4.10	8.20	0.118
	43.80	11.08	5.50	5.60	0.076
	54.80	17.00	6.80	10.50	0.097
	56.20	10.13	6.20	13.10	0.117
	65.60	24.00	11.10	13.00	0.079
	67.50	28.30	9.70	18.60	0.110
					Av. 0.098

*The solid phase left after filtration was dissolved in acid and the activity associated with it was measured by a liquid counter; total Sc^{46} present in the solid phase was thus ascertained.

†A known amount of ammonium dichromate was added to each and the amount of dichromate left in the solid phase was determined volumetrically. This dichromate was a measure of the scandium activity adhering to the solid phase.

**The percentage of Sc^{46} uptake was computed by subtracting the values in column (2) from those in column (1).

TABLE II

*Co-precipitation of scandium with ammonium ferric alum at diff. temp.*Conc. of Sc = $3.5 \times 10^{-2} M$.

Temp.	Alum pptd.	Solid phase.		Sc uptake.**	D_4
		*Gross activity.	Adhered mother liq.†		
$-1.8^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$	36.00%	7.59%	3.59%	4.00%	0.074
	48.80	11.50	6.40	5.10	0.066
	57.20	14.22	8.20	6.50	0.052
	71.20	21.50	10.90	10.60	0.052
					Av. 0.057
$1.5^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$	45.48	17.75	11.80	5.95	0.076
	61.60	23.33	13.50	9.83	0.068
	70.50	31.47	18.80	12.87	0.062
					Av. 0.068

TABLE II (contd.)

Temp.	Alum pptd.	Solid phase.		S uptake.**	D.
		Gross activity	Adhered mother liq.†		
2.5°±0.5°	50.60%	15.61%	7.50%	8.11%	0.988
	58.70	20.65	10.00	10.13	0.979
	64.30	24.42	10.00	14.42	0.983
					Av. 0.986
4°±0.5°		Data in details are shown in Table I.			0.988
6°±0.5°	47.00	17.00	10.00	7.00	0.985
	52.00	17.85	10.00	7.85	0.972
	57.10	21.53	11.10	10.43	0.987
					Av. 0.981
7°±0.5°	35.30	7.33	2.80	4.53	0.987
	48.80	12.70	4.90	7.80	0.988
	60.00	18.40	8.30	10.10	0.975
	71.50	22.10	9.00	13.10	0.961
					Av. 0.978
10°±0.5°	41.33	3.30	4.10	4.20	0.982
	58.30	15.25	6.85	8.40	0.984
	64.50	19.80	11.00	8.80	0.953
					Av. 0.960
20°±0.5°	41.50	23.40	14.00	9.80	0.148
	51.60	25.06	16.00	9.05	0.063
	56.50	29.30	20.00	9.30	0.079
	60.20	31.80	22.00	9.60	0.072
					Av. 0.975

N. B. Symbols have the same significance as in Table I.

TABLE III
Co-precipitation of indium with ferric alum.

Temp. = 4°±0.5°.

Conc. of indium.	Alum pptd.	Solid phase.		Indium uptake.**	D.
		*Total activity.	Adhered mother liq.†		
5×10 ⁻⁵ M (tracer)	30.90%	21.65%	13.68%	7.92	0.193
	42.30	30.50	17.88	12.62	0.197
	50.66	35.37	18.94	16.43	0.190
	63.33	46.95	24.22	23.73	0.170
	68.26	57.71	31.58	26.41	0.167
					Av. 0.183
3.4×10 ⁻²	47.40	20.10	6.70	13.40	0.172
	58.60	30.40	10.00	20.40	0.180
	66.10	40.00	15.60	24.40	0.166
					Av. 0.173

*The solid phase left after filtration was dissolved in acid and activity associated with it was measured by a liquid counter. Indium activity present in the solid phase was thus ascertained.

†A known amount of ammonium dichromate was added to each and the amount of dichromate left in the mother liquor was determined volumetrically. The deficiency in (NH₄)₂Cr₂O₇ in the mother liquor was a measure of indium activity adhering to the solid phase.

**The percentage of In¹¹⁴ uptake was computed by subtracting the values in column (2) from those in column (1).

We could not proceed above $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ scandium due to paucity of the material. The results in these regions show that the distribution factor becomes constant within statistical fluctuations. In consideration of the analogy of iron and scandium, uptake of scandium through mixed crystal formation may be a positive evidence of the existence of the scandium alum.

Incidentally, we kept sufficient margin as regards the attainment of equilibrium in our study of the distribution factor. Fig. 1 shows that it requires about 48 hours for the attainment of equilibrium in internally formed crystals.

FIG. 1. Distribution of Sc^{46} between $\text{NH}_4\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2$, 12 H_2O crystals and its saturated solution in H_2SO_4 medium at 4° , showing the attainment of equilibrium.

In our study with both In^{114} and Sc^{46} , we have all along equilibrated the solid phase in contact with the saturated solution for at least 72 hours, thereby ensuring attainment of equilibrium between the tracer in the solid and that in the solution.

It has already been mentioned that because of low partition value we had to take recourse to special devices to avoid washing and at the same time to measure activity from the solid phase which contained 4 to 18% of the tracer scandium in question. That $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ is a measure of the mother liquor adhering to the solid was examined by trial experiments, already mentioned.

The detailed study² of the heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) in known systems with Ga^{67} , Fe^{59} as guests and potassium chroms alum and potassium aluminium alum as hosts has revealed that alums are mixed crystals, forming in all proportions. To gather additional support, we have selected another known system like In^{114} as guest and ammonium ferric alum as host, where ammonium indium alum is well known and where the value of the homogeneous distribution factor (D) is comparable to that of scandium. A study was made exactly in the same way as was done in the case of scandium. Table III shows that distribution factor D is constant. This known system was investigated in tracer scale as well as in finite concentration of the guest ion. In the present study every possible precaution has been taken to verify the constancy of D .

That D value decreases with decrease in the concentration of scandium may be ascribed to existence of different complex ions in solution. Scandium is well known to form tri-scandium sulphate; in extreme dilution in presence of such a high concentration of anion, the concentration of the disulphate ion may be reduced to such an extent as not to effect any appreciable uptake of the tracer by the host lattice. Possibility of the formation of ammonium-complex of scandium, analogous to chromamine, cannot also be discarded. D -values in Table I indicate that scandium alum is highly soluble. Existence of different complex ions in solution may also have a considerable effect on such a poor uptake.

2. Purkayastha and Das, this *Journal*, 1963 40, 163.

3. Purkayastha and Sarker, unpublished work.

Fig. 2 shows the effect of temperature on the value of D of the system. The value of D , though constant at a particular temperature, increases with increase in temperature.

Fig. 2. Variation of the distribution factor (D) with respect to temperature.

Highest value of D is at 4°. At still higher temperature, its value, though constant at a particular temperature, assumes a diminishing trend and at 20° (Table II) constancy of D vanishes altogether. Prominent rise from -2° to 4° can be accounted for by assuming that scandium alum is less soluble than the host alum with increase in temperature. A sudden break at the neighbourhood of 4° may be related to transition temperature³ of the guest alum. Indirect inferences can therefore be derived that scandium alum will never be isolated at a temperature above 4°.

This particular issue requires further study. This inference is based on the assumption that ammonium ferric alum, the host lattice, does not undergo any morphological change in between the temperatures which have been investigated.

Details as regards the transition temperature and isolation of scandium alum remain yet to be completed.